

PSYCHOLOGICAL SCIENCES

HUMAN AGGRESSIVE BEHAVIOR AS A PROBLEM OF PSYCHOLOGY

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Abstract

In the article the author deals with the problem of aggressive behavior as one of the main problems of psychology. This problem is the main direction of research psychologists around the world. Elevated levels of aggressive behavior, according to the author is associated with social, economic and other factors. In recent years, it is proved that the media, movies also lead to aggressive behavior. To establish the aggressive behavior of the students Western University experiment was conducted Bass-Dark. As a result, we define different, but mostly physical and indirect aggression.

Keywords: aggression, aggressive behavior, physical aggression, verbal aggression, negativism, indirect aggression, aggression malignant, benign aggression, affect, expression, stress

Recently, the investigation of the problems of aggressive human behavior has become the main focus of research of psychologists around the world. Many articles and books have been published on this topic. International conferences, symposia and seminars on this problem are organized in Europe and America. Because the level of violence and aggression is increasing in modern times. Throughout history, humanity has faced situations that manifest themselves in the form of oppression, violence, conspiracy, destruction and other destructive actions that bring material and spiritual pain to people. Every day, we receive information from the mass media about crimes, wars, and terrorist acts, which are the embodiment of people's aggressive behavior. History proves that aggression is an integral part of human social life. Also, aggression has a strong appeal and is contagious. Most people deny the so-called aggression, but they display it widely in their daily lives. In everyday life, we use the word aggression to describe certain types of behavior, from comic interviews to brutal death.

What is aggression in general? Aggression (from the Latin word aggressive attack) is individual or group behavior, physical or psychological damage, injury or destruction of another person or group. Nowadays, the term aggression is used very widely. They associate this term with both negative emotions and negative motives, as well as negative orientations and destructive activities.

In psychology, aggression is understood as a tendency manifested in real behavior or fantasies in order to subjugate or dominate others. This tendency is universal, and the term "aggression" itself has a neutral meaning. In essence, aggression can be negative aggression aimed at satisfying a positive, self-aggressive tendency that serves vital interests and life. Aggression can be used to achieve a certain goal, just as the purpose of aggression is to inflict pain. Aggression can be directed either at external objects or at oneself. Aggression directed at people is especially dangerous for society.

Internal representatives of aggression can be ideas, fantasies, and affects. For example, a person can live

with the idea of applying dice to someone. Someone only reckons with the person who hurt them in their fantasies and has a strong affect. Aggressive tendency can be manifested by various aggressive affects. The intensity of aggressive affects is correlated with their psychological functions. Aggression performs important functions for an individual, such as protecting autonomy, eliminating the source of danger or suffering, overcoming obstacles on the way to satisfying needs, resolving internal conflict, and increasing self-esteem. In this case, the actions of a cold-blooded hired killer should not be considered aggression. This seems absurd. Attempts to link my aggression with a motive do not seem convincing. For example, no one can call it aggression when parents punish their child for any misbehavior. However, the motive to intentionally harm here is unquestionable. It is not always possible to evaluate aggression in terms of cognitive process. In many cases, aggression is directed against loved ones who have a pleasant moment and a positive attitude [2, p. 250-252].

One of the most intense and complex aggressive affects is undoubtedly hatred. The main goal of a hater is to destroy the object of aggression. Under certain conditions, hatred and the desire for revenge can be inappropriately intensified. If they become a stable characteristic *ustanovka*, we can already talk about the character reaching the limit of psychopathology. In the case of "milder" pathologies, hatred takes the form of gross moral prohibitions and aggressive affirmation of personal ideals. Also, hatred can manifest as desire for power, subjugation or destruction. In more severe forms, the tendency to sadism manifests itself in the desire to make its object suffer and enjoy it. The most severe form of manifestation of hatred is to destroy or consider everything radically worthless. Hatred can also be expressed in self-hatred, for example, when the "I" is identified with the object of hatred and self-destruction becomes the only way to eliminate it. Relationships with the object of hatred are especially valuable for the aggressor's personality.

In the depths of his heart, he is simultaneously directed to the destruction of the object of his hatred and

to the preservation of relations with him. Kernberg pointed out that hatred probably plays the role of a vengeful triumvirate both on another person and on oneself (to a certain part of one's "I"), which currently instills a sense of horror in a person and demands revenge for past suffering. Hate is a form of manifestation of aggressive tendencies, which, according to psychoanalytic views, are as natural for man as libido in the broadest sense of the word is a manifestation of sexual inclination. It is known that in his theoretical work, Z. Freud tried to justify aggression as an innate self-destructive tendency towards death. However, this view was not widely accepted. Until now, there are discussions about the formation of life conflicts and frustrations on the basis of whether the aggressive tendency is innate (pre-born-destructive) or other active orientations.

More interesting ideas about the formation of aggression are explained in the works of E. Fromm "Human soul" and "Anatomy of human destructiveness". Fromm divides aggression into benign and malignant types. The first is game aggression, which is more often found in sports competitions. Here, the goal is not to kill or injure the opponent, but to demonstrate quickness and skill. Another type of benign aggression is the self-assertive tendency to achieve a goal. Such aggression is important for self-affirmation. A business manager, a brilliant politician, a bold researcher can have this kind of aggression to achieve their goal. Of course, a defensive tendency aimed not at destroying the goal, but at preserving life, also belongs to benign aggression.

Malignant forms of aggression include aggression caused by envy and jealousy. At this time, a person commits violent acts not only because he cannot achieve what he wants, but also because someone else has it. Another type of aggression is revenge aggression. Unlike defensive aggression, since the damage has already been done, it has no protective function. He is trying to undo what has already happened. This has a more wonderful meaning than reality. There is also aggression associated with the loss of trust. E. Fromm writes: "Loss of faith in life leads to hatred. Man tries to prove that life is cruel, all people are cruel, and you yourself must be cruel [2.p.255].

There are a large number of factors that can curb aggression in people with a tendency to aggression or, on the contrary, provoke aggression in people who do not have such a characteristic. From this point of view, a person's outlook on life, moral value system, relations with social environment, individual and collective self-awareness are of great importance. It is also necessary to mention the gender factor. Aggressive behavior in women is more related to the expression (excitement) of anger and manifests as a method of solving a conflict situation. In men, aggression plays the role of a tool to achieve the set goal. While men prefer direct aggression, indirect aggression is typical for women. Also, men act more often as the object of aggression. This is probably due to the fact that women pose less of a threat to potential aggressors. Experience shows that women are more victims of sexual violence.

Another group of factors that provoke aggression is related to the environment. For example, according to the archives of the US Federal Bureau of Investigation, the number of violent crimes increases during hot summer months, especially in hot climate cities. It has been established that a lot of noise has a negative effect on relationships between people. Economic factors play a major role in the formation of aggressive behavior. Numerous studies confirm that violent acts are more common among the lower social classes of the population. Poverty, illiteracy, and unemployment greatly weakens a person's ability to achieve their goals, thus strengthening the tendency to aggressive actions. The development of medical services and the possibility of using them should be added to the list of important social factors. Timely detection and treatment of mental disorders associated with dangerous forms of behavior significantly reduces the risk of mental illness committing aggressive acts.

The use of alcohol and drugs also causes aggressive actions. Thus, a drunk person cannot use normal, non-aggressive mechanisms to the full extent, and the possibilities of self-control and adequate assessment of the situation decrease sharply. In many cases, alcohol is the main cause of sexual aggression. One of the important social factors that increase the likelihood of aggression is the availability of weapons.

Aggressiveness is often revealed among representatives of subcultural types who prefer non-traditional life, for example, among those who live in a number of adolescent and youth groups or in a criminogenic environment. In such an environment, it is common for cruelty to be accepted as socially acceptable, even admirable behavior. The main source of aggressive behavior of teenagers is their relationship with their families. Aggressive teenagers, as a rule, grow up in families with a large psychological distance between parents and children, little interest in children's development, lack of care and affection, and a preference for using force, especially physical punishment, instead of care and conversation. For most teenagers, the main source of vivid examples of aggressive behavior is the family. Adolescents who see their parents experience physical aggression in relation to each other tend to create similar situations in relation to others.

Adolescents learn different types of behavior in the process of interaction with other children. Different types of aggressive behavior also arise during communication with peers. In addition, they can learn patterns of aggressive behavior also when interacting with their peers. The last source is mass media.

Cultural factors affecting aggressive behavior include information media, movies, and computer games. Aggressive tendencies have been proven to increase after watching films rich in violent scenes. It is assumed that the influence of mass media occurs through the activation of specific memories and emotions in the memory.

Aggression and aggressiveness mean the personality's reaction to an unfavorable and harmful environment. Aggressiveness is a personality trait and is characterized by destructive tendencies in subject-subject relations. That is, the process aimed at eliminating and

destroying obstacles is a characteristic sign of aggressiveness. A certain degree of aggressiveness is observed in the personality when conflict situations are not resolved and there is a deprivation of moderate mutual relations.

A. Bassa and A. Dark developed a test-questionnaire consisting of 75 statements regarding the definition of aggressiveness in teenagers and young adults. Here, 8 types of aggressive reactions are classified and it is determined which of them predominates in young people [4, p. 213-214].

1) Physical aggression - application of physical force to other persons.

2) Indirect aggression or unmediated - aggression that is not directed at another person or anyone.

3) Irritability- as soon as you get a little irritated and angry, rudeness of negative reactions and quick loss of balance is observed.

4) Negativism - not reacting in the form of active or passive behavior against laws, rules and traditions.

5) Resentment, feeling of hatred and envy towards actual and intended actions.

6) Suspicion covers the range from treating others with caution and mistrust to harming other people.

7) Verbal aggression - don't express your negative feelings through words (threats, curses, cursing).

8) Feeling of guilt - the feeling of being a bad person and suffering from conscience.

To test aggression, Bassa-Darki questionnaire was applied to 20 students of the Western university, 10 girls and 10 boys. According to the conducted research, different types of aggression were found in the applied persons.

So, while physical aggression and negativism were detected in boys, irritation and unmediated aggression were found in girls. However, guilt and verbal aggression prevailed in both groups. In the course of the research, there were no resentment and suspicion types of aggression.

An aggressive person can lose everything he has gained in life by his behavior. Everyone gets upset, angry, angry and wants to express their aggression when faced with a situation. At this time, a person may shout, say obscene words, and even use force without paying attention to ethical rules. In general, most people have a desire to act aggressively. Sometimes even a person is not satisfied with expressing aggression in words, he wants to hit someone or break something. These desires sometimes reach such a level that a person cannot control his anger and behaves completely aggressively.

But how to prevent aggressive behavior? What should be the preventive measures taken for this? If aggression continues for a long time, it becomes stronger and it becomes difficult to stop it. Also, as you try to hide and suppress aggression, it manifests itself in a worse form next time. Aggression is also difficult to control. Therefore, it is better to take preventive measures in order not to be exposed to aggression in advance. For this, it is recommended to do sports. You can spend time with your favorite art form or your favorite music. In order to get rid of aggression, it is recommended not to react immediately to stress, to stay away from negative thoughts.

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